

Figure 5K: PS6 Film

P 56 3.23.18

Figure 5K Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-3 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: **Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 5: **I-ASD-3 Veh**, Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: **I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5K: GAPDH for PS6 Film

Phospha Gapdh # 3.27.18

Figure 5K Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-3 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL) , Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: **Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 5: **I-ASD-3 Veh**, Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: **I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

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Figure 5K: Total S6 Film

Total S6 3.23.18

Figure 5K Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-3 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL) , Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: **Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 5: **I-ASD-3 Veh**, Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: **I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5K: GAPDH for
Total S6 Film

Total
GAPDH

3.27.18

Figure 5K

Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-3 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: **Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 5: **I-ASD-3 Veh**, Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: **I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)**
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

#2 ✓

#3 ✓